

Lumbar Disc Herniation: Etiology and Recovery

Dr. Xinghong Yang*

Department of Infectious Diseases & Immunology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Florida, P.O. Box 110880, Gainesville, FL 32611-0880, Florida, United States

WebLog Open Access Publications
Article ID : wjor.2025.i2704
Author : Dr. Xinghong Yang, Ph.D.

Abstract

Lumbar Disc Herniation (LDH) is a common and debilitating condition that often persists or recurs despite conventional medical treatments. It imposes substantial physical, psychological, and social burdens on patients. Modern medicine can offer temporary relief through conservative therapy or surgery, but these approaches do not address the deeper karmic causes that underlie LDH, such as killing karma and the attachment of spirits (souls of deceased humans or animals), which can lead to ongoing suffering and relapse. This paper presents nine key teachings from Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu and seven case studies demonstrating that practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door (心灵法门) through Three Golden Buddhist Practices – making vows (许愿), reciting Buddhist scriptures (念经), and performing life liberation (放生) – enables patients to eliminate karmic obstacles and achieve complete recovery from LDH. This article proposes a novel, profoundly effective pathway for healing LDH that transcends conventional medical approaches.

Keywords: Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door; Golden Buddhist Practices; Lumbar Disc Herniation; Karma; Spirits; Recovery

Introduction

Lumbar disc herniation (LDH) is a prevalent condition primarily resulting from lumbar intervertebral disc degeneration and nucleus pulposus protrusion, commonly presenting with low back and lower limb pain. It is characterized by a prolonged disease course and high recurrence rate, often causing persistent suffering and substantially impairing patients' quality of life and mental health [1]. The prevalence of LDH has risen with the aging population, frequently necessitating neurosurgical intervention [2].

Conventional management ranges from conservative therapies, such as physical therapy, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, muscle relaxants, and epidural steroid injections, to surgical procedures like microdiscectomy or laminectomy in severe or refractory cases [3]. While many patients benefit from conservative care, some experience persistent or recurrent symptoms, and surgical outcomes remain unpredictable and often non-durable [4].

Given the multifactorial nature of LDH, encompassing mechanical, biological, and psychosocial components, interest has grown in complementary and alternative approaches addressing broader aspects of health and well-being [5–7]. Although these approaches may offer partial symptom relief and functional improvement, none have demonstrated a complete cure.

We previously reported a case of LDH that achieved complete recovery through the practice of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [8]. This patient had generated substantial killing karma and experienced two miscarriages; after resolving this karma and helping the spirits of her miscarried children ascend, she recovered fully and has remained free of recurrence.

To further elucidate the therapeutic potential of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, this paper presents Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu's teachings on LDH alongside seven case reports demonstrating how these Buddhist practices may facilitate profound and lasting recovery.

Mechanisms & Solutions

LDH with discogenic low back pain and sciatica is a common yet complex musculoskeletal disorder. Its underlying mechanisms remain poorly understood, and no definitive therapies exist for LDH-induced pain [9]. Common interventions, including pharmacological treatments and epidural steroid injections, lack robust, high-quality evidence supporting their long-term effectiveness beyond temporary symptom relief [10].

Where conventional medicine faces these limitations, Buddhism offers an alternative

OPEN ACCESS

*Correspondence:

Dr. Xinghong Yang, Department of Infectious Diseases & Immunology, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Florida, P.O. Box 110880, Gainesville, FL 32611-0880, Florida, United States,
E-mail: yangxh@ufl.edu; dr.yang.ttk@gmail.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8063-430X>

Received Date: 18 Sep 2025

Accepted Date: 25 Sep 2025

Published Date: 27 Sep 2025

Citation:

Xinghong Yang. Lumbar Disc Herniation: Etiology and Recovery. WebLog J Orthop. wjor.2025.i2704. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17291050>

Copyright© 2025 Dr. Xinghong Yang. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

perspective. Building on our previous success in addressing LDH through Dharma practices [8], this study examines nine key insights from Master Lu that illuminate the karmic mechanisms underlying LDH and propose spiritual solutions aimed at achieving complete and lasting recovery.

Q&A 1. Previous-life fish raising, this-life cooking and selling snails, leading to LDH [11]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on June 16, 2015)

Caller: Thank you, Master Lu! My lower back... they said I did something wrong in my past life. May I ask you, Master Lu, what I did in my past life that made me have LDH?

Master: Let me have a look.

Caller: I have had surgery.

Master: You had surgery on the third vertebra.

Caller: Yes, lumbar spine.

Master: Between the third and fourth lumbar vertebrae. I can see now... In your previous life, you... raised fish.

Caller: I did not raise fish. I used to be a chef, and later I had a stall selling snails in the night market.

Master: That is a big problem. You did not catch my first words. I said you raised fish in your previous life. Listen to the recording again.

Caller: Oh, thank you, Master Lu.

Master: You raised fish in your past life, and in this life, you created new karmic debts again, so now you have trouble.

Caller: Yes, yes.

Master: Your lower back is indeed suffering retribution now. The pain is very severe.

Caller: Yes! It relapsed in 2006 and lasted until 2008. I was in terrible pain for two years.

Master: It was killing you with pain. Think about it. You kept killing those beings... How many negative karmic ties have you formed with them?! You must not do that. Really, you must not.

Caller: Oh. How many Little Houses do I need to recite for my karmic creditors, Master Lu?

Master: To heal your back, you need to recite 320 Little Houses.

Caller: Okay, thank you, Master Lu. I will definitely recite them well.

Q&A 2. Women's lower-back karmic obstacles often come from aborted children; spirits like to stay where karmic obstacles are heavier [12]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on March 29, 2015)

Caller: Hello, Master! Every time I ask you to check my totem, there are always spirits seen at my lower back. I wonder, does that mean my lower back has heavier karmic obstacles?

Master: Your lower back must have heavier karmic obstacles. Generally speaking, for women, heavy karmic obstacles at the lower back are usually because of having had abortions.

Caller: Master, I have never had an abortion, and I have never

been married.

Master: If you have never had an abortion, maybe your mother had, and the spirit is seeking you... Generally, spirits all attach themselves to a woman's lower back, with their feet stepping on your lower back and their hands pulling your neck. So, women who have had abortions often suffer from lower back and neck problems.

Caller: Each time there is a different spirit in this area; one leaves and another comes, always on my lower back.

Master: Yes, they like that place.

Caller: How can I remove the karmic obstacles in this area?

Master: Once all spirits are gone, no one will come anymore. Let me give a simple example: like the monkey hill in a zoo where monkeys like to gather. If you change the monkey, it still goes to that same hill, swinging around, because that place suits it. Only when there are no monkeys will no one go there anymore.

Q&A 3. What to do for LDH (1)? [13]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on August 13, 2019)

Caller: Hello, Master! I want to ask about a woman born in 1982, the Year of the Dog. Please check her lumbar spine. She injured it before, and it has never recovered.

Master: The third vertebra is herniated, LDH.

Caller: Yes. How many Little Houses does she need to recite?

Master: She should do hot compresses, recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and she needs to recite about 108 Little Houses for her karmic creditors.

Caller: Okay. Have her aborted children been ascended?

Master: They have. I just saw that she is protected by a Bodhisattva.

Caller: May I ask which Bodhisattva?

Master: Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Caller: Gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva! Gratitude to Master!

Q&A 4. What to do for LDH (2)? [14]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 12, 2018)

Caller: Hello, Master! Before I started practicing Buddhism, I got a back injury during training. Now I have LDH pressing on a nerve. How can I eliminate this pain through Buddhist practice and reciting Buddhist scriptures?

Master: First, sleep on a hard bed. Don't be afraid. Once you get used to it, it is very comfortable.

(1). A hard bed keeps your spine straight. A soft bed lets your spine sink, which is bad.

(2). Let me first explain from the physical aspect. Do wall squats: squat down with your back against the wall, then rise up again, about ten times a day. This forces the lumbar disc back in place.

(3). Keep your chest upright when walking and standing.

(4). While reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*, rub both sides of your lower back with your hands.

(5). Do hot compresses. Heat softens the protruding disc so you can gently push it back in. If you push it back frequently, it will be less

likely to pop out again.

Caller: Understood.

Master: Also, poor sitting posture can easily cause it to protrude. So be careful with your sitting posture. People who practiced Buddhism in the past would say: "Stand like a pine, sit like a bell." Stand straight like a pine tree, and when sitting, put something to support your back. If you really can not sit upright, at least place a cushion behind your lower back.

Caller: Okay. What about reciting scriptures?

Master: If no spirits are involved, mainly recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*. If there are spirits, recite Little Houses. I am not reading your totem right now. If you have nightmares, that means there are spirits. Then, recite 49 Little Houses at a time, and afterwards continue in batches of 21 each.

Caller: Okay.

Q&A 5. Precautions for LDH and how to ensure surgery success [15]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 4, 2013)

Caller: Master, the hospital wants me to undergo surgery. They said I have LDH. Sometimes I can not even walk.

Master: This condition will not get much better even with surgery, and without surgery, it is also like this. For this kind of problem:

- (1). Protect your lower back from getting cold.
- (2). Pay attention to your sitting and sleeping posture.
- (3). Recite more Buddhist scriptures, especially the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for help.

If you do surgery, they will actually saw off a bit of the bone to reduce friction.

Caller: Yes, they said they would insert something inside.

Master: Putting something inside can help, but for some people, the outcome is not ideal.

Caller: Yes, yes.

Master: They will explain everything to you. If the pain is really unbearable, then go ahead with surgery. If you can tolerate it, try to protect it well. Problems like this usually come from not protecting your bones properly.

Caller: I see. Master, I currently recite 49 *Great Compassion Mantras*, 3 *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance*, 9 *Heart Sutras*, 49 *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhous*, 21 *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*, and 21 *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* daily.

Master: How long have you been practicing with Master?

Caller: Two years.

Master: If you have practiced for two years, it is okay to have surgery.

Caller: Is it okay?

Master: Reciting these scriptures will ensure your surgery is successful.

Caller: Oh.

Master: Keep reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra* and pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to bless you.

Q&A 6. LDH improved a lot after practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [16]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 1, 2014)

Caller: Master, I was born in 1970, the Year of the Dog. Could you please check my back?

Master: Your lower back is slightly herniated.

Caller: Yes, I have LDH.

Master: And one of your kidneys, the left one, is not very good.

Caller: Yes.

Master: Your LDH feels better when lying down, but once you stand for a while, it hurts again.

Caller: Yes, yes. Before practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, it was so serious that I almost needed surgery and could hardly move. But after persisting in practicing for one month, it improved by 50%. However, the remaining 50% took a long time.

Master: Yes, it is not easy. Completely eliminating all karmic obstacles is very hard.

Caller: Yes.

Q&A 7. LDH Healed After Practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [17]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 19, 2014)

Caller: I would like to share an experience: I used to practice another Dharma Door. Two years ago, I came across Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and found it very good. At that time, I had LDH, and the doctor advised surgery. I did not go through with it because I believed I could recover by reciting Buddhist scriptures, so I kept reciting. Later, I even dreamed that Master Lu was blessing me and healing me. Now I have basically fully recovered without going back to the hospital for any treatment. I just kept reciting scriptures, soaking my feet as you taught, and lightly tapping my legs and doing light exercise.

Master: Yes.

Caller: And as a result, my body recovered.

Master: Now you know, right?

Caller: I am grateful to Master Lu and to Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

Master: You must practice diligently. It is also very important that when I bless you, you understand?

Caller: Yes.

Q&A 8. Severe LDH Healed Without Surgery After Reciting Buddhist Scriptures [18]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Jan. 30, 2011)

Caller: My younger brother had a severe LDH in August. It was very serious at that time. I once tried calling you but could not get through. I was so worried I almost cried. Later, we called the Secretariat, and they told us how to recite. We persisted in reciting together. He was originally scheduled for surgery because he had already lost movement in his lower body due to spinal canal stenosis

compressing his nerves. We recited for more than twenty days — my husband, my brother, and I. He actually recovered. When others suggested hospitalization again, he told them it was no longer necessary. He had already arranged for surgery, but now he did not need it because he said he was completely fine and pain-free.

Master: Yesterday, I even heard about another listener who had already put on surgical clothes and was about to be wheeled into the operating room. While he was reciting, the doctors looked at his scan and told him the problem was gone and surgery was no longer needed.

Caller: Oh!

Master: He had already changed into those thin paper-like surgical clothes. Can you see how miraculous the Bodhisattva's blessings are?

Caller: Truly amazing!

Master: Very amazing. So keep reciting diligently!

Caller: A lot of incredible things have happened during this period of practice.

Master: You should write them down and share them so others can benefit. This will bring you even more merits and virtues, understand?

Caller: Yes, I understand.

Master: Submit it to the Secretariat to post on the blog so everyone can benefit.

Caller: Understood.

Q&A 9. Illnesses That Doctors Cannot Heal Are Actually Karmic Illnesses [19]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov. 18, 2012)

Caller: Hello, Master! Is lumbar disc stenosis or narrowing of the spinal bones considered a karmic illness?

Master: Yes, they are karmic illnesses. Any disease that doctors cannot heal is a karmic illness. Diseases that doctors can heal are physical illnesses; those that cannot be healed are karmic illnesses.

According to Master Lu's teachings, LDH may arise from karmic causes rooted in acts of killing in past or present lives, such as raising fish, cooking, or selling snails. These actions create killing karma, which can lead to spirits attaching to the lower back. Among such back issues, the attachment of aborted children's spirits is especially common in women. These karmic obstacles can manifest physically as pain and a disc protrusion.

Master Lu recommends resolving these issues through a combination of spiritual and physical approaches. Spiritually, practitioners should (1) make vows, (2) recite Buddhist scriptures, especially the *Great Compassion Mantra* and Little Houses dedicated to karmic creditors, (3) perform life liberation, and (4) pray to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for blessings. Physically, He advises sleeping on a hard bed, maintaining correct posture, doing wall squats to realign the spine, rubbing the lower back while reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and applying hot compresses to soften and reposition the disc. If surgery becomes unavoidable, maintaining steady recitation practice can help ensure its success.

Practitioner testimonials in Q&A 6-8 show symptom relief or

complete recovery from LDH without surgery, reinforcing Master Lu's assertion that illnesses untreatable by doctors are often karmic illnesses that can be healed by eliminating karmic debts and helping attached spirits ascend.

Results

The following are seven case presentations by practitioners of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

Case 1. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Is True and Incomparable — It Restored My Physical and Mental Health

I used to believe that I must have done a lot of evil in my past lives and failed to cultivate properly, which is why I suffered so much in this life...

Before practicing Buddhism, I was cheerful yet strong-willed and extreme in temperament. I was easily irritated and never yielded to others. Whenever things did not go my way, I would get upset and lose my appetite, feel depressed, and could not let things go even after they passed. This led to my life becoming full of frustration and chaos.

In 2022, by chance, I met several young fellow Buddhist practitioners of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door who were like long-lost friends despite our age differences. I actively sought their guidance and followed them into this Dharma Door. Afterwards, I began listening to Master Lu's recordings, reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and reciting Little Houses for my karmic creditors. I have been quite diligent for over a year now. What has benefited me most are reciting Little Houses, performing life liberation, and making vows.

After practicing Buddhism, I learned from Master Lu's recordings that some illnesses are karmic illnesses, which must be resolved through the "Three Golden Buddhist Practices" of making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation while praying for the blessings of the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva. So, I knelt before the Buddhist altar and prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help me overcome my life's tribulations. I made vows:

- (1). Never kill;
- (2). Never drink alcohol;
- (3). Be a vegetarian for ten days each month;
- (4). Recite Buddhist scriptures diligently;
- (5). Spread Buddhism online;
- (6). Release 100,000 fish over 20 years;
- (7). Recite 1,000 Little Houses for my karmic creditors within 3 years, in batches of 21;
- (8). Read 3 chapters of *Buddhism in Plain Terms* daily;
- (9). Perform life liberation on the 1st and 15th days of the lunar month when conditions allow.

Looking back now, it feels truly miraculous! I have completely emerged from my previous life of frustration and chaos. Now, I am filled with Dharma joy every day, serving my elderly father and spending all my spare time reciting scriptures.

My chronic dry mouth, which felt like Sjögren's syndrome and

worsened when drinking water, which lasted for 2-3 years, has healed. My chronic pharyngitis has healed. My severe toenail fungus has healed. My superficial gastritis has not recurred. Many other minor ailments have also disappeared without treatment!

Importantly, my LDH, which had caused pain for two years, is also completely healed.

I once ignorantly had four abortions, but now those spirits have been ascended.

Throughout the process, I firmly believed in the power of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. As long as I recited diligently to help those spirits ascend, made vows, performed life liberation, and created merits and virtues, I would recover. Indeed, thanks to my unwavering faith and perseverance, my back pain disappeared. I am so moved that I kneel and bow to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva every day.

I am deeply grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva and to my benevolent Master Jun Hong Lu for bringing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to the human world, which has helped me awaken from delusion, let go of attachments, sleep peacefully at night, and temper my personality. Life has become so much lighter. Buddhism is truly wonderful!

Here, I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to Namo Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva! The Bodhisattva is truly compassionate and responds to all sincere prayers. With utmost sincerity, I want to tell everyone: Practicing Buddhism is truly wonderful! The scriptures left to us by the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas carry immense power. Practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is even better, and Master Lu's recordings are so profoundly beneficial.

I will practice diligently, focus on one Dharma Door, do more good deeds, and persist in reciting Buddhist scriptures. Only in this way can I repay the great kindness of Guan Yin Bodhisattva and the compassionate guidance of my benevolent Master.

Shared by: C152

Case 2. The “Three Golden Buddhist Practices” Miraculously Healed My Over 10-Year LDH

I had an LDH protruding 0.5 cm for over ten years. Every winter, when the weather turned cold, the pain became unbearable, and I had to be hospitalized for treatment each year. I used to practice another Dharma Door, reciting thousands of lengthy Buddhist scriptures for over ten years, waking up early and sleeping late to chant, yet I always wondered why all that effort brought no effect. My pain never lessened. I even blamed my mother for giving birth to me with such a frail body, not only with back pain but also heart palpitations, suffering both physically and mentally.

In 2016, I met a fellow Buddhist practitioner at work who was reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*. She told me that the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is very effective and kindly gave me Buddhist scriptures and blank Little Houses free of charge. I started performing daily recitations that very day. A week later, I began reciting Little Houses.

After learning Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I finally understood that my illnesses were caused by karmic obstacles. I also understood that not all mantras and sutras are suitable for lay practitioners to recite. From then on, I firmly believed in Guan Yin Bodhisattva and

in Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door as the Dharma Door most suitable for me. I followed the teachings, persevering in reciting scriptures, making vows, performing life liberation, and adopting a vegetarian diet. In 2017, I fulfilled my wish to set up a Buddhist altar and invited Guan Yin Bodhisattva into my home.

Over the past four years of practice, I have introduced 13 new people to Buddhism. I have recited around 2,000 Little Houses and now read 6–8 chapters of *Buddhism in Plain Terms* daily. On the Mid-Autumn Festival of 2019, I vowed to release 100,000 fish, including 30,000 dedicated on behalf of Master Lu. So far, I have released 80,000.

Through continuous vows, scripture recitation, and life liberation, my LDH unknowingly healed, and my heart palpitations also disappeared. The “Three Golden Buddhist Practices” truly cured both my body and mind. They are incredibly efficacious, and Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is one of the most extraordinary Dharma Doors in this Age of Dharma Decline. I am deeply grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and to my benevolent Master!

Words cannot express the miraculous power of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door or the joy I feel in my heart. All I feel is gratitude—endless gratitude! I have personally experienced the inconceivable power of Buddhism. The Bodhisattvas are truly by our side! As long as we have faith, vows, and diligent practice, we will witness miracles. Merely waiting only wastes time and severs our wisdom-life. Keep going, fellow practitioners—Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is truly miraculous!

Without Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I would not have a complete family today. Treasure life and nurture your wisdom-life. As long as life continues, never stop practicing Buddhism!

Dharma practitioner: W153

Case 3. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door Gave Me a New Life — I Threw Away My Crutches, and My Back No Longer Hurts

On Easter in 2013, I was busy working at a restaurant when suddenly my lower back hurt so badly that I could not move. I forced myself to finish the shift and return home, knowing that a great calamity had befallen me. My son was far away in the city. Gritting my teeth, I placed some bread and water by my bed, then collapsed and could not move again. The next day began my long journey seeking medical treatment.

Medical scans showed that I had a herniated disc between my third and fourth lumbar vertebrae, severely compressing the nerves and causing mobility impairment. The entire lower left half of my body was numb with a tingling sensation. I could not sleep at night and was in unbearable pain. Doctors strongly recommended surgery, but I still hoped to find a turning point in traditional Chinese medicine. I tried everything from massage and acupuncture to physical therapy, running everywhere with hope each time, only to return disappointed. I did not want to spend the rest of my life in a wheelchair, yet cruel reality struck me again and again.

Finally, I was referred to a doctor for comprehensive treatment. After reviewing my case and listening to my story, instead of discussing my condition, the doctor asked, “Do you know how to recite Buddhist scriptures?” I was surprised and nodded, replying, “I can recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*.” The doctor said, “Then go

home and recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* sincerely.” Holding the book *Fate, Fortune and Feng Shui* that I had received in the waiting room, I returned home and began reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*. When the pain kept me awake at night, I read this precious book that changed my destiny. The miraculous examples in the book rekindled my hope and often brought me to tears. If only I had known about this Dharma Door earlier, my husband might not have passed away so soon.

In July 2013, I finally found the Guan Yin Hall in Melbourne, Australia. When I hobbled in on crutches and stood before Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I was in my sixties, yet I felt like a child seeing her mother, and tears streamed down my face. Decades of suffering that no one had listened to, only the compassionate Bodhisattva would.

Under the guidance of fellow Buddhist practitioners, I began to recite daily homework and Little Houses. At first, it took me 3-4 days to complete one Little House, but I firmly believed that as long as I put in the effort, Guan Yin Bodhisattva would surely have compassion for me.

After just over two months, although still in pain, I no longer needed my crutches at all. What a tremendous change that was! This change inspired me to become more diligent, and I was able to recite five Little Houses each day.

By January 2014, I had recited over 900 Little Houses for my karmic creditors. My back pain was completely gone!

Shared by: H154

Case 4. Recovery from LDH Through the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

In August 2014, my elder brother developed LDH (with a hemangioma on the third vertebra, and herniation of the fourth and fifth vertebrae pressing on the nerves) while working, which left him bedridden and unable to walk.

I advised him to make a vow to release 500 fish, which was completed on the first day of the lunar month.

Miraculously, the very next day, he stood up from bed without any back pain. Afterwards, my aunt, my mother, my sister, and I each recited a few Little Houses for his karmic creditors. He was able to walk again!

He was deeply convinced by the miraculous power of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and finally became a believer. Since then, he has gradually recited about thirty Little Houses.

His LDH has fully recovered. This is truly a miracle!

Shared by: L155

Case 5. Healed My LDH with 7 Little Houses

I am a new Buddhist who had just begun learning Buddhism shortly before the 2020 Spring Festival. After about a month of practicing daily recitations, I started reciting Little Houses. Within just one week, I had completed reciting 7 Little Houses.

On the morning of the 15th day of the second lunar month, I burned and offered these 7 Little Houses to my karmic creditors at 8:00 a.m. Around 10:00 a.m., I suddenly felt very sleepy, so I went to take a nap. In my dream, an old friend brought a stranger to treat the LDH that had plagued me for more than ten years. Everyone knows that LDH is not easy to cure. That stranger pressed on my back and

said, “It is cured!” Then I woke up.

I quickly told my family that someone had just treated my back in a dream and that my back was healed, but they did not believe me. That evening, I shared the dream with a fellow Buddhist practitioner, and the practitioner told me it was Guan Yin Bodhisattva who had come to heal me! Although the dream felt very real, I was still somewhat doubtful that I could be cured just like that.

About a month later, I went back to my hometown for personal matters and visited an orthopedic doctor to check my lumbar spine. The doctor said, “Your back is fine now!” Hearing that my LDH was healed, I was overwhelmed with joy and gratitude for the compassion of Guan Yin Bodhisattva! After burning just 7 Little Houses, my LDH was miraculously healed. The vertebra that had previously been sunken had now become flat. Only then did I fully believe in the boundless power of Guan Yin Bodhisattva. She truly responds to every sincere prayer. The Little Houses are truly miraculous.

I hope my sharing today can help more destined sentient beings. Let us follow Master Lu’s footsteps in spreading the Dharma, becoming one of the hands and eyes of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, so that more people can encounter the Dharma, awaken wisdom, and break through delusion.

Shared by: C156

Case 6. Recovering from Over a Decade of LDH Through the Blessings of Guan Yin Bodhisattva

I am an ordinary retired teacher, 76 years old this year. I had suffered from LDH, osteoporosis, and other bone diseases for more than ten years. As I grew older, the condition became much more severe and frequent in the past two years. From the end of 2013 to August 2014, nearly ten months, I was in such excruciating pain in my lower back and legs that I could neither sit nor stand, let alone walk. Despite seeking medical treatment everywhere, nothing worked.

My daughter urged me to recite Buddhist scriptures diligently and help ascend the spirits of the deceased. During those ten months, I endured the physical pain while wholeheartedly reciting scriptures, allowing my mind to settle down. Without the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, I truly cannot imagine how I could have survived those painful days!

Perhaps my sincerity moved Guan Yin Bodhisattva with Great Compassion. In August 2014, introduced by someone in my hometown, and I went to a local hospital, where they helped arrange a consultation with experts from a major hospital. Miraculously, on the day of my surgery, the hospital happened to invite South Korean specialists to promote a new surgical technique and offered to perform surgeries free of charge for several patients. I was very fortunate to be selected.

On the day of the surgery, I was nervous at first. But once I entered the operating room, I kept silently reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra*, and surprisingly, I felt no fear at all. The surgery was a great success. After I was discharged, I gradually improved. I am able to stand and sit again.

That day, three of us underwent the operation, all performed by the South Korean experts. The other two were younger than me. One was slightly over 50, and the other was only 45. However, they later had to undergo several more surgeries, which brought no improvement. Today, they still live in painful torment. As for me, an

elderly patient who was on the verge of paralysis, I recovered better and better each day.

By December, I felt no pain at all and have been living a happy and normal life!

I want to kowtow tens of thousands of times and offer tens of thousands of thanks—gratitude to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva! Gratitude to the living Bodhisattva, Master Jun Hong Lu!

Shared by: C157

Case 7. LDH That Troubled Me for 22 Years Ends *via* the Bodhisattva's Compassion

In 2016, my younger sister invited me to attend a Dharma conference in Penang, Malaysia. I went with my mother and a close friend, thinking of it as just a sightseeing trip. At that time, we were only planning to “drop by” the conference out of curiosity.

In my life, I had met many so-called “masters” with their devoted followers, so this Dharma Door did not impress me at first. I felt, “Your Master is yours, not mine.” However, when I arrived at the conference venue, I was completely astonished.

As a senior corporate executive, I viewed the event through the lens of organizational management. A Dharma conference with tens of thousands of attendees was flawlessly coordinated solely by volunteers, from the planning to the pre-event, mid-event, and post-event phases. Every detail of the service was thoughtful and almost perfect. I realized that this Dharma Door deeply cultivates and elevates people's character and quality. That sparked my curiosity to learn more.

I have always considered myself a rational person who examines things critically. In this process, I am deeply grateful to my young cousin, who patiently found a skillful way to guide me into Buddhism without pressure.

My cousin and I often discussed life and shared insights. She gradually shifted our conversations toward Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door—topics like the difference between merits and virtues (功德) and good deeds (善事), the law of cause and effect (因果定律), the cycle of birth and death (轮回), and how to apply Buddhist teachings in daily life. She even invited me into a study group.

Through this, I watched her grow wiser and more capable. I began to acknowledge the Dharma Door, but practicing it myself felt impossible, especially becoming a vegetarian. I had been a meat lover my whole life; when I was young, my dream was to marry a butcher.

That wish even came true. My husband was in the beef and lamb business, a supplier for a famous noodle brand. I was so obsessed with meat that my parents would bring their own vegetables when visiting, because my home had none.

Reciting Buddhist scriptures also seemed impossible, as I was in the busiest period of my career. So, for a long time, I only studied Buddhism theoretically without truly practicing.

During this stage, something extraordinary happened that made me feel the Bodhisattva's blessing. One night, I was leaning against my bed, participating in the study group of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. I suddenly saw a hazy figure enter my room and stand by my bed. We looked at each other for a few seconds, and I instinctively said, “Don't stay here, and I'll go downstairs.” The next morning, I

had completely forgotten it.

At about 6:45 a.m., there was a loud crash. My husband and I ran upstairs to find that a 150 × 90 cm radiator had fallen right onto the spot where I had been leaning the night before. The bed frame was deformed. Had I been lying there, my head would have been crushed. Terrified, I immediately remembered the figure I saw the night before.

I told my cousin, and she said this was the Bodhisattva protecting me because I had been participating in the study of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. The Bodhisattva had given me a second life. She encouraged me to start reciting Buddhist scriptures to show my gratitude.

So I began reciting, and I also made a vow to eat vegetarian meals on the 1st and 15th of each lunar month. My cousin never forced me to go fully vegetarian, but often encouraged me to perform life liberation.

One day after work, I casually went to release a few dozen big carp. When I saw them happily swimming away, I was deeply moved. Just a small effort from me gave them the hope of a new life. This touched the innate compassion deep in my heart—my Buddha nature that had been buried under ignorance and karmic obstacles. Tears streamed down my face. I thought, “I can do more.” Right there, I vowed to become fully vegetarian.

To support my vow, I asked all my staff to also eat vegetarian on the 1st and 15th days of every lunar month. I even joked with our cook that if she forgot to cook vegetarian, she would lose her job. Now, nearly 100 employees in my company follow this, and many say eating vegetarian food makes them feel healthier and lighter.

I had suffered from LDH for 22 years. Last month, it suddenly flared up. Normally, this would require hospitalization, but I had an important event I could not miss. Coincidentally, that day I had planned to do life liberation with fellow Buddhist practitioners.

Limping in pain, I still went to release lives, praying to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to help eliminate my karmic obstacles in my waist. On the way, I even transformed another person to learn about Buddhism. That very night, my waist miraculously stopped hurting. I canceled the hospital appointment.

Because my work involves training others about mindset and understanding people, I often incorporate *Buddhism in Plain Terms* to help people see things more clearly, resolve their troubles, and find solutions. More and more people open up to me about their problems, and I guide them toward Buddhism, encouraging some to do life liberation, others to start reciting Buddhist scriptures.

Once, a grandmother brought her 5.5-year-old grandson to the resort I manage. I sensed he was different from other children. He had been diagnosed with depression since birth, and no experts or even psychics could help him.

I told his grandmother, “I know a world-renowned Master who has healed many children like him. Your grandson's problem would be like a minor cold to him. We can try.”

She was skeptical but agreed. The boy sat motionless for an hour, staring blankly at an apple. I slowly recited the *Heart Sutra* to him. Gradually, he set down the apple and looked at me, his gaze softening. I said, “Shall we shake hands?” and he immediately did. Then I said, “Can we hug?” and he opened his arms. As I hugged him, I felt such

compassion, as if he were my own child, and tears ran down my face. His grandmother also cried.

She asked, "What did you chant? I'll pay you." I said, "I do not want money. It seems my Master is truly extraordinary. Buddhism can help you." She asked if she could learn, and I replied, "If you truly want your grandson to get well, I will teach you." She started learning Buddhism and reciting scriptures, and the boy gradually improved. She now messages me daily to share his progress.

As for myself, I have recited just over 30 Little Houses for my karmic creditors and dreamed of ascending 7 children and 1 elder. I also often dream of someone treating me or of going to the toilet to eliminate karmic obstacles.

After less than a year of practice, I feel vibrant, with no signs of menopause. I am joyful every day and full of energy at work. Previously, I worried that reciting would disrupt my life and work, but now I know those fears were groundless.

I am deeply grateful to my cousin, who spent four years patiently guiding me. She never forced me, only gently used skillful means to help me move from rejection to diligence. Now she encourages me to take responsibility for spreading the Dharma, to help more sentient beings, and to study further at the Guan Yin Citta Practice Centre.

Shared by: N158

Across all 6 cases, the core methods used were consistent: making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, performing life liberation, adopting vegetarianism, and praying to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for blessings. Some practitioners also incorporated reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms* and spreading the Dharma.

Overall, these testimonies report substantial or complete remission of LDH symptoms through Dharma practice rather than medical intervention, supporting the notion that karmic obstacles can be cleared and health can be restored via the Three Golden Buddhist Practices.

Discussion

LDH affects approximately 1% to 3% of the population annually and imposes substantial physical, quality-of-life, and productivity burdens [10]. From elucidating its underlying mechanisms to achieving a complete cure, modern medicine has thus far achieved limited progress.

The mechanism of LDH was clearly explained by Master Lu (Q&A 1-9). Although Cases 2-6 did not disclose their causes, Cases 1 and 7 showed that killing karma was the main cause of their LDH. Case 1 had aborted four children, while Case 7 was found to have the spirits of seven children and one elderly person attached to her body. Previously, we have reported that the impact of abortion on a person's health and life trajectory is far beyond what ordinary people and even medical professionals can imagine [20]. Cases 1 and 7 serve as new supporting evidence of this.

With a clear understanding of the karmic and spiritual mechanisms underlying LDH, patients can actively eliminate karma and help attached spirits ascend, ultimately achieving recovery from LDH. Once one understands this fundamental principle, it becomes clear why Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door has proven effective not only for mental [21-23] and neurological [24-27] disorders, but also for skin [28-32], genetic diseases [33-35] and cancer [36, 37]. Although

these diseases may seem entirely unrelated, they can all benefit from Buddhist practices and achieve recovery because they share the same underlying pathogenic mechanisms: karma and spirits. To resolve karma and liberate spirits, one can universally apply the Golden Buddhist Practices.

Buddhas possess supreme wisdom, and for those learning Buddhism, developing the wisdom of the Buddhas is just as important as cultivating their compassion. The wisdom of Buddha is fundamentally different from worldly wisdom.

What is worldly wisdom? Case 7 was undoubtedly a person with worldly wisdom. For example, she was highly knowledgeable, had risen to a managerial position in her company, earned a high income, and even married a meat supplier, fulfilling her wish to enjoy abundant meat. While worldly wisdom is not always harmful, it may lead people to create more karmic obstacles.

By contrast, Case 7's young cousin may not have been as intelligent or as financially successful as her, yet this cousin possessed the wisdom of Buddha. With such wisdom, one can refrain from creating new karma while gradually eliminating old karma. Because N158 had not believed in Buddhism at that time, she lacked the wisdom of Buddha. She herself continued to suffer intermittent torment from LDH and create new karma from eating the flesh of sentient beings. Her cousin maintains a joyful life without suffering. This is the contrast difference between owning human wisdom and Buddha wisdom.

We, Buddhist practitioners, must hold high the torch of wisdom to illuminate the Sahā world [38].

Buddhism often speaks of enlightenment, also called "awakening." Case 7 vividly exemplifies what enlightenment means. After performing life liberation, her Buddha nature was awakened. She resolutely vowed to become a vegetarian and even encouraged her company's employees to eat vegetarian food on the 1st and 15th days of each lunar month (*Please note: These two days are considered major holy days when Buddhas and Bodhisattvas descend to the human world to observe sentient beings. How could Buddhas and Bodhisattvas bless those who eat the flesh of sentient beings?*)

Through the wisdom of Buddhism, N158 ultimately freed herself from the suffering caused by LDH. After attaining awakening, she began to help others on their own paths to liberation. She devoted herself wholeheartedly to spreading the Dharma and even helped the boy with depression.

In fact, we previously published two reports demonstrating that depression can be completely cured [8, 21]. In contrast, modern medicine still does not fully understand the causes of depression, how to prevent it, and how to cure it.

Dharma does not reject medical treatment; rather, it embraces it. Case 6 is an example. The patient practiced Dharma to address his LDH while also undergoing surgery. From a scientific perspective, his observation that only one out of three patients he knew recovered after surgery may seem anecdotal, but the fact he pointed out is objective: surgery does not always resolve LDH, even when performed by highly skilled doctors from South Korea. In fact, recurrent LDH occurs in 5% to 24% of cases and is the most common cause of surgical failure and the need for revision surgery [39].

Another noteworthy point from his observation is that he was the only one who fully recovered after LDH surgery. If this were a

mere coincidence, then why do such positive outcomes consistently occur among those who practice Dharma? C157's recovery was by no means coincidental. Like the other six cases, it shows that Dharma itself can heal LDH. When combined with surgery, Dharma enabled him to achieve complete and normal recovery.

Thus, Case 6 illustrates how surgery addressed the symptoms while Dharma treated the root cause. This is exactly what Master Lu has always advocated.

In our previous reports on Alzheimer's disease and Schizophrenia [24, 40], we have consistently advocated that medical doctors practice Buddhism, particularly the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. This benefits not only the doctors themselves but also their patients. Case 3 is a clear example. The doctor, apparently a follower of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, recognized that LDH is a karmic disease that cannot be cured solely through medicine. Therefore, the doctor recommended that the patient seek help from Buddhism. The result turned out to be remarkably successful.

Given that 1 - 3 out of every 100 people worldwide suffer from LDH, and that doctors can only relieve the symptoms with medication but cannot cure it, while the Dharma can truly cure it yet few have heard of this, it would be a groundbreaking initiative if doctors could learn and understand the Dharma, and, through the platform of medical institutions, help relieve the suffering of those with LDH. After all, medicine and the Dharma ultimately share the same goal — to heal and save people.

Conclusion

LDH remains a challenging condition for modern medicine, often leading to chronic pain, disability, and frequent recurrence. The seven cases presented demonstrate that the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door's Three (or Four or Five) Golden Buddhist Practices can effectively eliminate the karmic causes underlying LDH and facilitate profound recovery, even when conventional therapies fail.

This case study suggests that karmic obstacles, particularly those arising from killing karma and attached spirits, are a fundamental root of LDH. Resolving these karmic obstacles through Buddhist cultivation can restore physical health and mental well-being.

While Dharma does not reject medical treatment, it addresses the root causes beyond the reach of medicine, offering a complementary path to healing. The results underscore the need for further exploration of Dharma practices in curing LDH and other intractable conditions, and invite medical professionals to consider the benefits of integrating Dharma wisdom into their own practice for the sake of their patients and themselves.

Acknowledgments

Dharma practitioners Shangen, Rachel, and Purple assisted in the manuscript preparation process. Their work is greatly appreciated.

Conflict of Interest

No.

Financial Support

None.

Ethical Statement

The author did not take part in any part of the experimental

design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenters were done by themselves independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The 9 Q&As and 7 case presentations in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

Disclaimer of Liability

The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioner may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

In the event of an emergency, it is crucial to promptly contact your doctor or emergency services by dialing 911. Relying on any information found in this paper is done solely at your own risk. The author bears no responsibility for the consequences. By using or misusing the contents, you accept liability for any personal injury, including death. It is imperative to exercise caution and seek professional medical guidance for health-related concerns.

References

1. Chai Y, Shen X, Wang Z, Zhang X, Wang Z, Zuo X, Liu J. Lumbar disc herniation reabsorption: a review of clinical manifestations, mechanisms, and conservative treatments. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2025 Jul 28; 12: 1633762. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2025.1633762.
2. Corazzelli G, Corvino S, Ricciardi F, Pizzuti V, Leonetti S, D'Elia A, Santilli M, Aloj F, Innocenzi G. Perioperative management of antithrombotic therapy in elderly patients undergoing lumbar discectomy: a retrospective study on 163 patients. *Neurosurg Rev*. 2024 Oct 21; 47(1): 807. doi: 10.1007/s10143-024-03059-8.
3. Lee JS, Lee SB, Kang KY, Oh SH, Chae DS. Review of Recent Treatment Strategies for Lumbar Disc Herniation (LDH) Focusing on Nonsurgical and Regenerative Therapies. *J Clin Med*. 2025 Feb 12; 14(4): 1196. doi: 10.3390/jcm14041196.
4. Sacks GI, Destefano V, Fiore SM, Davis RP, Ahknoukh S, Mushlin HM. Predictive Factors for Outcomes Following Surgical Treatment of Lumbar Disc Herniation. *Int J Spine Surg*. 2024 Sep 20; 18(6): 637-44. doi: 10.14444/8650.
5. Lee J, Ha IH, Kim MR, Cho HW, Seo JY, Choi HS, Song KC, Shin BC, Shin JS, Lee YJ. Pain, disability, and MRI changes in lumbar disc herniation patients treated with integrative medicine: Ten-year results of an observational study. *Integr Med Res*. 2022 Jun; 11(2): 100833. doi: 10.1016/j.imr.2022.100833.
6. Li T, Wang S, Zhang S, Shen X, Song Y, Yang Z, Huang Z. Evaluation of clinical efficacy of silver-needle warm acupuncture in treating adults with acute low back pain due to lumbosacral disc herniation: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2019 Jul 31; 20(1): 470. doi: 10.1186/s13063-019-3566-2.
7. Kim MH, Lee YJ, Shin JS, Lee J, Jeong H, Kim MR, Park SM, Go U, Kim

- SM, Kim JY, Hwang DG, Ha IH. The Long-Term Course of Outcomes for Lumbar Intervertebral Disc Herniation following Integrated Complementary and Alternative Medicine Inpatient Treatment: A Prospective Observational Study. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2017; 2017: 5239719. doi: 10.1155/2017/5239719.
8. Yang X. Treating Rare and Intractable Diseases via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J*, 2024; 18(5): 1137.
9. Liu CC, Zhang XS, Ruan YT, Huang ZX, Zhang SB, Liu M, Luo HJ, Wu SL, Ma C. Accumulation of methylglyoxal increases the advanced glycation end-product levels in DRG and contributes to lumbar disk herniation-induced persistent pain. *J Neurophysiol*, 2017; 118(2): 1321-1328. doi: 10.1152/jn.00745.2016.
10. Bhandutia A, Yang M, Liu Q, Gao Y, Liu J, Liu S, Guo A, Chauhan K. Real-world treatment patterns and management gaps of lumbar disc herniation in the United States. *N Am Spine Soc J*, 2025; 23: 100757. doi: 10.1016/j.xnsj.2025.100757.
11. Lu JH. Previous-life fish raising, this-life cooking and selling snails leading to LDH. *Zongshu* 20150616 17: 32. 2015.
12. Lu JH. Women's lower-back karmic obstacles often come from aborted children; spirits like to stay where karmic obstacles are heavier. *Wenda* 20150329B 42:50. 2015.
13. Lu JH. What to do for LDH (1)? *Zongshu* 20190813 07:14. 2019.
14. Lu JH. What to do for LDH (2)? *Wenda* 20180112 01:09:24. 2018.
15. Lu JH. Precautions for LDH and how to ensure surgery success. *Wenda* 20130104. 2013.
16. Lu JH. LDH improved a lot after practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Zongshu* 20141101 49:32. 2014.
17. Lu JH. LDH Healed After Practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Wenda* 20140119A 07:05. 2014.
18. Lu JH. Listener's Feedback: Severe LDH Healed Without Surgery After Reciting Buddhist Scriptures. *Wenda* 20111030 01:37:17. 2011.
19. Lu JH. Illnesses That Doctors Cannot Heal Are Actually Karmic Illnesses. *Wenda* 20121118. 2012.
20. Yang X. Abortion: Unimaginable Consequences and 'Regret Medicine'. *Invest Gynecol Res Women's Health*, 2025; 5(3): 490-511. IGRWH. 000618. DOI: 10.31031/IGRWH.2025.05.000618.
21. Yang X. Severe Depression: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *Haya Saudi J Life Sci*, 2024; 9(11): 427-446. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sjls.2024.v09i11.004>.
22. Yang X. Oppositional Defiant Disorder: Underlying Mechanism and Solutions. *WebLog J Fam Med*. *wjfm*.2025.a1502. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15873702>
23. Yang X. Borderline personality disorder: Healing through dharma practices. *Epidemiol Public Health*, 2025; 3(1):1064. doi: 10.52768/3065-0011/1064
24. Yang X. Alzheimer's Diseases are Reversible from a Dharma Perspective. *Health Sci J*, 2024; 18(6): 1145.
25. Yang X. Myasthenia Gravis Is Curable via Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J*, 2024; 18(9): 1175.
26. Yang X. Parkinson's Disease: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *WebLog J Alzheimers Parkinsons Dis*. *wjapd*.2025.b2501. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15873815>
27. Yang X. Epilepsy: Etiology, Pathogenesis, and Cure. *Neurosurgery and Neurology Research*, 2025; 2(2): 1-17.
28. Yang X. Eczema: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *WJDC*. 2024; 1(3):1-16.
29. Yang X. Healing Chronic Urticaria Through the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Saudi J Nurs Health Care*, 2024; 7(12): 369-374. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sjnhc.2024.v07i12.004>
30. Yang X. Efficiently Curing Dyshidrosis. *WebLog J Dermatol*. *wjd*.2025.c1901. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15873871>
31. Yang X. Psoriasis: True Etiology and Complete Cure. *WebLog J Immunol*. *wji*.2025.i0301. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17092324>
32. Yang X. Vitiligo: Etiology and Cure. *Skin and Dermatological Research*. 2025; 3(1). DOI: 10.58489/3066-4942/005
33. Yang X. Etiology and Treatment of Glutaric Aciduria Type I. *J Clin Med Img*, 2024; 8(3): 1-13.
34. Yang X. Etiology and Treatment of Prader-Willi Syndrome. *EAS J Biotechnol Genet*, 2025; 7(1): 13-18. <https://doi.org/10.36349/easjbg.2025.v07i01.002>
35. Yang X. Down Syndrome: Root Causes and Pathways to Recovery. *Advances in Neurology and Neuroscience*, 2025; 8(1): 01-14.
36. Yang X. Surviving Late-Stage Cancers by Practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. *Health Sci J*, 2024; 18(7) :1155.
37. Yang X. Breast Cancer: True Causes and A Natural Path to Healing. *Journal of Cancer and Oncology Care*, 2025; 1(1): 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.61615/JCOC/2025/SEPT027140904>
38. 卢军宏 (2020) 无明显是烦恼的根。2020年1月22日《白话佛法》广播讲座第十八集
39. Colantonio DF, Fredericks DR Jr, Elsenbeck MJ, Cady C, Schlaff CD, Christensen DL, Helgeson MD, Wagner SC. Recurrent Lumbar Disk Herniation and Revision Surgery Rates After Single-Level Lumbar Microdiscectomy in the Military Population. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg*, 2024; 33(18): 1040-1047. doi: 10.5435/JAAOS-D-24-00879.
40. Yang X. Schizophrenia: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention. *Journal of Neurology and Neurosurgery*, 2025; 1(1): 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.61615/JNN/2025/FEB027140215>.